

An Investigation That the Method of Determining the Parameters of Policy Tools is Highly Political in Itself

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Abstract

The method by which economists determine the parameters of policy instruments is in itself highly political (Breslau, 1997b; Espeland , 1998; Evans, 1999). Later, organizations seeking to profit from this or that approach, such as telecommunications firms, engaged and supported experts whose expertise supported their perceived interests. Examples of such organizations are AT&T, Verizon and Sprint (Guala , 2001; Nik- Khah , 2008). Finally, the policy tools used by economists will have political, normative, cognitive, and symbolic effects, but these will often disguise these effects (Ashmore et al., 1989; Ferguson, 1990; Porter, 1996; Barry, 2002; Espeland and Vannebo , 2007). They help determine which actors can legitimately intervene in a situation (Breslau, 1997b; Espeland , 1998), shape what policy options can be discussed (Ferguson, 1990; Breslau, 2013), and shift the discretion to different parties. Breslau, 1997b; Espeland , 1998; Breslau, 1997a; Breslau, 1997b; Espeland , 1998; Ferguson, 1990; Bres (Espeland and Vannebo , 2007). They also serve as a form of "institutionalized cognition" that not only produces new objects of

knowledge such as economics (Mitchell, 2002), growth (Miller and Rose, 1990) or credit scores (Poon, 2009; Carruthers, 2010), but also new categories of thought. (Carruthers & Espeland, 1991; Valverde, 2003) and they direct attention in certain ways. Mitchell (2002), growth (Miller & Rose, 1990) or credit scores (Poon, 2009 (Miller & Rose, 1990; MacKenzie, 2011) We will address these issues below. places limits on what can be fully synthesized. in how expert knowledge influences policy, they place agency in very different places. Both the socio-technical tools of scientific research methods and the ideas and concepts presented in the political literature have a similar emphasis. This is primarily the possession of knowledge rather than the effects people have This article concentrates particularly on the socio-technical tools of scientific research methods as well as on concepts with a similar emphasis on ideas and concepts presented in the political literature.

Keywords : *Economists' Policy Tools, Economists' Policy Parameters, Economists' Policy Making Methods, Policy Tools, Policy Parameters, Policy Determination Methods*

1. Introduction

This is one of the parallels between the two. The latter, on the other hand, ensures that knowledge, people, and material things are closely interconnected. Consequently, he argues that the ideal unit of analysis should be this heterogeneous community rather than the ideas themselves. However, there are certain recurring themes that can be seen in more than one study. There are three empirical results that seem very convincing . To begin with, policy recommendations made by economists are more likely to be effective in some situations than others. In particular, economists will have a greater impact in ill-defined situations, which can include both times of crisis (Blyth , 2002) and moments early in the policy process, such as problem identification and agenda setting. This is because ill-defined situations allow more room for comment and discussion (Brint , 1990; Keller, 2009). This conclusion is consistent across the literature on ideas, politics, and the professions, and is likely to apply to a wide range of political situations, provided government is at least heavily bureaucratized. They will also have a greater impact when they can frame certain policy issues as

fundamentally technical and therefore uniquely competent to address. This finding is particularly robust as it covers the literatures of ideas and politics (Hall , 1993), epistemic communities (Ikenberry , 1992; Lindvall , 2009), and occupations (Halliday , 1987; Jacob, 1988) and seems likely to apply as well. In various bureaucratic contexts, for example, Hall (1993) has found that epistemic communities (Ikenberry , 1992; Lindvall , 2009) are more likely to share a common epistemic framework than occupations (So, to understand the influence of economists on public policy, it is necessary to understand that the manner in which it identifies certain areas within its exclusive jurisdictions and as those areas that need the application of specialized knowledge. According to the advice of experts, it is likely that the majority of economists' influence will be exerted by means other than direct advice or formulation of policy decisions. Eyal (2013) and Rose (1992)) explanations, the results of social economics are not the same as those of economists. In many different written works, it has been suggested that what really happened. how it reconstructs meat.

2. Economic Discourses and the Potential for Political Influence

Similarly, economic discourses that later spread beyond their original domains have the potential to produce political effects. In the broadest sense, concepts such as "economy" (Emmison , 1983; Mitchell, 1998) or "growth" (Collins, 2000) enable new kinds of conversations, and the rational, self-interested concept of homo economicus shapes policy makers. perceptions of how people behave. [Emmison , 1983; Mitchell, 1998; Collins, 2000] (Callon , 1998a). In addition to the implications of specific concepts, more general arguments based on economic theories can reshape political dynamics (Berman , 2012) and the authority of economic knowledge can legitimately justify policy choices (Breslau , 2013). More broadly, published research in the field of occupations (O'Connor, 2001; Eyal , 2006; Eyal et al ., 2010), studies of science (Ferguson, 1990; Scott, 1998; Mitchell, 2002), ideas and politics (Schmidt, 2008; Schmidt, 2010) highlights how expert discourse influences political action. As a result, a number of different studies have pointed to the importance of middle-level social orders – particularly professional or disciplinary fields and organizations – in mediating the influence of economists on public policy. Particularly from

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the literature on occupations , we see that the structure of the field of expertise has a significant impact on policy action (Abbott, 2005; Fourcade , 2009; Mudge and Vauchez , 2012).

It is possible that experts are working towards their goals in both of these areas at the same time. If this is the case, disciplinary agreements about what constitutes valid knowledge may influence the work that experts undertake in the policy area (Breslau , 1997a). And if we look at a few research organizations, we see that organizational dynamics influence the influence of experts. Although this finding is often not explicitly stated in organizational terms, literature on ideas and politics (Eisner , 1991; Chwioroth , 2010), literature on epistemic communities (Gutiérrez , 2010), literature on occupations (Eisner , 1991; Chwioroth , 2010), is generally consistent. Halliday , 1987; Babb , 2001, 2007) and studies in science research are available (Halliday , 1987; Babb , 2001, 2007). (Vaughan, 1996; Eden, 2004; Millo and MacKenzie , 2009, 2011). A plan to learn about the role of economists In the preceding sections, we have conducted a literature review combining four different sources of information and compiled some consistent conclusions about the role played by economists and economic theory in the economy. These results are consistent with each other as a whole and contain very few instances of direct conflict and disagreement. In light of this preliminary summary, how should we most effectively initiate new research on the impact of the economy? We propose a new way of thinking about the factors that determine what constitutes an impact of a policy. Rather than starting with a political conclusion and then trying to explain whether economists' policy recommendations played a role in its formation, or starting with economists' policy advice and then exploring the political impact of those recommendations, we suggest focusing on three different issues.

In order for economists to be influential, they must first have a certain professional authority and then use this authority in various settings. They can have an impact by obtaining specialized institutional positions within the management mechanism. It can mean formal organizational work or it can mean important placements within social networks. And they can reshape the cognitive infrastructure of policymaking, either by propagating an economic reasoning—that is, by teaching policymakers to think about problems the way economists do—or by helping to build economic policy apparatuses. Policymakers see the world in certain ways (like GDP or unemployment rate)

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or help them make decisions. And they can do this either by spreading an economic reasoning, that is, by teaching policymakers to think about the same problems (such as cost-benefit analysis). We believe it would be helpful to divide the study into two components to better understand the implications of the economy for public policy. First, we need to examine the preconditions—how each of these sources of power—professional authority, institutional position, and cognitive infrastructure—is constructed and the role economists play in creating those conditions. The second step is to explore how various power sources affect public policy. Economists do not need to be successful in all three of these areas to have an impact on public policy. For example, under some circumstances, they may have substantial professional power, but only a limited capacity to establish policy mechanisms. Alternatively, their level of technical influence on data generation may be high, but their overall authority may be limited. However, the three modes tend to feed off each other in fundamental ways, a theme we'll return to in the next paragraphs.

3. The Need to Search Through Historical Studies

Overall, this typology indicates a need to seek the influence of economists in both specific and general ways, as well as through historical studies that cross the boundaries between the intellectual and political realms. 3.1 Credibility in the professional community The prestige, reputation and validity accorded to economists constitute what is known as their "professional authority". Therefore, this approach is not primarily concerned with the immediate effects of policy. Rather, it implies asking us why economists, unlike other types of experts, are seen as particularly interested and authoritative on certain policy issues. This type of research is necessary to understand how the profession gained power and then bestowed upon its members. Having professional authority means that economists are seen as the most qualified to conduct research on economics-related issues and their knowledge in this field is considered to be more reliable than other types of knowledge.

So far, research has focused on determining the importance of ideas, but less attention has been paid to factors that explain why some experts' opinions are taken seriously, but not others.

However, research on the professions has shown that professional authority has fluctuated throughout history, has become more global and has significant implications for influencing policy. In analyzing professional authority, it is necessary to understand not only how economists have acquired this authority, but also how this authority translates into policy implications. The rise of economics as a respected academic field in the United States in the 20th century is a well-studied example of how an academic field can gain professional credibility. The United States has become the center of a global network of economic expertise. As a result, the dynamics of the United States influence the production of economic knowledge and practices in countries all over the world. Although this tale has a national focus, it also has a global significance (Dezalay and Garth , 2008). Before 1900, there was no structural role for economists in policy making in the United States and little evidence of professionalization (Bernstein, 2001; Fourcade , 2009; Franklin, soon). Over the next few decades, their power steadily increased and the New Deal They played an important role in formulating the policies of the period (Barber , 1985, 1996; Bernstein, 2001). The most significant growth in the professional authority of economists, however, was during World War II. It occurred as a direct result of World War II. Economists have contributed to the daily challenges of war production, the larger problems of war financing and planning, and the sustained effort to allocate military resources more efficiently by contributing to a coherent and organized effort that helps the government manage wartime mobilization (Bernstein). , 1995; Guglielmo, 2008; Lacey , 2011). Samuelson (1944) noted their significant success during World War II. He attributed World War II to the fact that it was not just a war fought by physicists, but "an economist's war". In this particular scenario, at least, economists' achievements in policy analysis contributed to their increased professional authority. At the same time, more traditional institutional methods of doing economics were being phased out in favor of a more contemporary mathematical-Keynesian synthesis (Yonay , 1998; Weintraub , 2002; Rutherford, 2011). Attempts were made to elevate economics to a scientific discipline and, as a result, to gain greater respect as a discipline worthy of authority. The events that follow show how professional authority can have an impact on policy making.

4. Reducing or Eliminating Trade Restrictions Would Be Beneficial for the Economic Welfare of Less Developed Countries

For example, almost all economists are of the opinion that reducing or eliminating trade restrictions would be beneficial for the economic well-being of less developed countries. However, unilateral free trade is practically unheard of and there is not a single nation in the world that follows this policy. Why shouldn't they? More broadly, why do governments have such a hard time getting their economic policies right? Why is the advice of impartial observers, analysts and academics so often ignored? Policy is the typical answer and policy is typically the right answer. But this is a very general statement, comparable to suggesting that the economy determines the wealth of certain nations while others become impoverished. In what specific ways does policy hinder governments from making better policy decisions, especially in the face of impending emergencies? What does this teach us about how economic policy decisions can and should be made? The study of political economy focuses on how politics and economics both affect each other (see box). Governments are attempting to stimulate the economy towards elections to facilitate the so-called "political business cycles" characterized by the ebbs and flows of economic activity during elections . Likewise, the state of the economy also has a significant impact on the results of elections. In the past, political economists have uncovered the simple—and some might say disturbing—fact that the only piece of information we need to predict with a high degree of accuracy the outcome of presidential elections in the United States is economic growth and inflation rates (see, for example, the Fair 2018).

is generally accepted that the men who laid the foundations of modern economics were Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and John Stuart Mill . However, they called themselves political economists, and Mill's Principles of Political Economy was considered the most important work in the field from the time it was published in 1848 to the end of the century. These early thinkers failed to conceptualize the economic world and the political world as distinct from each other. Political analysis and economic analysis both followed two different models. The first step in this process was when governments began to loosen their direct control over the economy. Second, several political systems emerged: Europe moved from an almost entirely monarchical system to

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one that was more representative and with a wide variety of political structures. At the beginning of the 20th century, the fields of economics and political science emerged as distinct academic disciplines. This state of division continued through most of the 20th century. Because of the Great Depression and the difficulties associated with progress, only the economic challenges were challenging enough to keep economists busy. Likewise, the political issues of the period, including the two world wars as well as the emergence of fascism and communism, were so serious that they required separate consideration. By the 1970s, however, it was all too clear that the distinction between the political sphere and the economic sphere was misleading. This decade saw the decline of the monetary order established in Bretton Woods , two oil price shocks and stagflation ; All these events served to emphasize the intertwining of economic and political issues. The economy has become a central issue in politics, and a significant portion of the political discourse has focused on the economy. Over the past half century, political economy has emerged as an increasingly important topic in the fields of economics and political science in three different ways. It examines how political factors have an effect on the economy. The opinions of voters and interest groups have a significant impact on almost any economic policy that can be implemented. The goal of political economists is to determine which organizations are important, what interests they represent, and how political institutions affect the influence of groups on public policy.

Examines the relationship between economy and politics. The current state of the macroeconomics can help or hurt an incumbent's prospects. At the more microeconomic level, certain aspects of the economic organization or operations of certain businesses or industries may have an impact on the type and direction of their political activities. It can be said that this is valid both at the national and international level. Approaches political science through the lens of economics. It is possible to think of politicians as businesses whose components serve as customers, or governments as monopolistic businesses that provide their constituents with a variety of products and services. To gain a more solid theoretical understanding of the factors behind the surface of politics, academics simulate the connections between politics and economics. Each of these three approaches has had a significant impact not only on academics but also on policy makers. And political economy has a lot to offer both to people interested in analyzing how societies work and to those who want to

make changes in society. It all depends on where you live, right? The idea that any policy that is beneficial for society as a whole can be made good for everyone in society is one of the fundamental principles of economics. This is true even if politics creates winners and losers in society. Winners need some increase in taxation to compensate losers, and everyone will be in a better financial position as a result. Economists use powerful tools to determine which economic policies are most beneficial to society.

If that's the case, then why should economic policy be contentious? One of the basic tenets of political economy is that winners dislike the use of taxes to make up for losers. And now the battle has begun, not over what is best for society as a whole, but over who will come out on top and who will emerge from the losing side. What is in the interest of the nation may not be in the interest of my region, group, industry, or class; That's why I'm going to fight against him. Even in democracies, there is likely to be a significant number of citizens who believe that politics adheres to the golden rule; this indicates that whoever has the most gold sets the rules. Whether a country is democratic or not, special interest groups appear to play an important role around the world. These include powerful individuals, influential industries, large banks and corporations , tough labor unions and powerful labor unions . How else to explain the fact that the price of sugar in the United States is two or even three times the world average? Although there are 330 million people in the United States who consume sugar, there are only a few hundred sugarcane plantations and several thousand sugar beet farmers in the country. You might believe that 330 million people would have much more influence in politics than a few thousand, but you would be wrong to think so. For several decades, trade barriers and government subsidies contributed to the rise in sugar prices; this worked to the benefit of sugar plantation owners and farmers and to the detriment of everyone else. Why does a very small part of the sugar industry carry more weight than the rest of the nation? In the realm of political economy, it is a well-known fact that concentrated interests almost always prevail over scattered interests. Sugar farmers are highly organized and spend considerable effort in their efforts to influence political decision makers.

5. A Statement on the Protection of Trade

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It is essential for them to organize to defend and financially support politicians as they will be out of work if they are not treated favorably from the government. This is estimated to cost customers between \$2 billion and \$3 billion annually. Although it's a substantial amount of money, it's only a few cents a day for the typical American. No client will speak a dime a day to an elected representative or threaten to vote for a competitor on the matter. An explanation for trade protection can be found in the highly concentrated structure of producers as opposed to the dispersed nature of consumers. While a few automakers have the ability to organize themselves, tens of millions of people who buy cars do not. This is not the end of it. While management and labor in the automotive industry do not always agree on many issues, both automakers and auto workers agree that they want to be protected from the threat of competition from other countries. Politicians, especially in regions where automotive production is prominent, have a hard time rejecting the common demand of employees and owners of a strong business. This is especially true for politicians in regions where automobile production is vital. It is possible that this is not such a terrible thing. Sugar growers and auto workers depend on policies that are beneficial for their livelihoods. Who would suggest that the importance of employment should be ranked lower than the importance of reducing costs for customers? There is no generally accepted simple method for weighing potential advantages against potential costs. Is cheaper sugar really worth putting thousands of hard-working farmers out of work? Politics is a community's means of resolving differences between conflicting interests; therefore, those who have more to lose should probably have more say in this process.

In general, political economists avoid taking a stand on controversial moral and ethical questions of the kind discussed here. They try to grasp the factors that guide the society to take the decisions they make. The reason government policies favor sugar and vehicle manufacturers over consumers can be partially explained by the fact that sugar and auto manufacturers are much more at risk than sugar and automobile consumers and are much more organized. However, there is a certain user density. Sugar has a pleasant taste, and businesses that are members of the Sweetener Users Association want sweetener prices to drop. Companies like Coca-Cola and Hershey, among others, have made significant efforts to change the United States' sugar policy. The existence of

substantial vested interests on both sides of the issue helps explain why prices have not been higher than they are now. The same can be said for goods of industrial production. Steelmakers seek protection, but not steel users like automakers.

The struggle over trade policy is not just a conflict between large firms and individual families; rather, it is also a conflict between the big companies themselves. In such a case, we predict that every sector will be protected from competition and trade will be severely restricted worldwide. In fact, there are many influential interests in favor of international trade and investment. The free movement of both commodities and money is essential to the success of the world's multinational corporations and international banking institutions. This is especially true in modern days, when the success of many of the best companies in the world depends on complex supply networks around the world. In today's world, a typical multinational company creates parts and components in dozens of nations, assembles these products in many more countries, and then distributes the finished products around the world. These supply networks are disrupted when there are trade barriers, so many of the largest companies in the world are also some of the most ardent advocates of freer trade. Professor Jeffrey In this fifteen-minute video, Frieden addresses questions on political economy posed by viewers around the world. A twisted network The political arena serves as a battleground for various groups, including voters who take opposing positions on all issues, and vested interests . However, norms of political behavior can be quite different from one nation to another. Who wins in the struggle to control politics is influenced by the structure of the political economy. Elections are a logical starting point, at least in democracies where elections are held.

Governments that cannot meet the needs of their citizens cannot survive for very long as political entities. Consequently, we must anticipate that democracies will choose policies that are in the general interest of the economy. On the other hand, the economy as a whole has no voting rights. Politicians depend on electoral votes to win elections. The voters who matter or matter in an election are different in every nation due to the various electoral systems and social divisions. The ideal people to target are undecided voters in most political systems, as these individuals are more likely to change their votes in response to the incumbent platform or the commitments made by the challenger. Especially if the rich vote to the right and the poor to the left, the middle class is

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likely to be the determining factor in this election. In previous presidential elections in the United States, the Midwest has been the most economically depressed and host of the most critical votes. The majority of voters in these regions are of the opinion that the decline in manufacturing is due to competition from other countries. This helps explain why presidential candidates are becoming more protectionist, even though the vast majority of Americans want trade openness. Also, policy makers in democratic countries need to keep an eye on the next election; if they do not, they are likely to lose their position as policy makers. This helps explain why it can be difficult for governments today to invest money in programs that will only achieve long-term benefits such as pandemic prevention and preparedness.

Specifically, there are an overwhelming number of private and general interests in Population. It is easier to understand with the support of institutions. First, there are social institutions that can be thought of as forms of self-regulation by individuals. Some companies, farmers and workers are very well organized, which gives them greater political influence. Farmers in prosperous countries make up a very small percentage of the population, but they are well organized and receive almost universal subsidies and protections. In underdeveloped countries, farmers are many, but they are rarely organized and almost always taxed. As in many countries in northern Europe, when workers in a country are organized into central labor federations, they are given an important say in the formulation of national policy. Politics is structured differently in different countries, as societies organize themselves in various ways, such as by economic sector, geography, or ethnicity . Political institutions mediate between the demands of the voters and the decisions made by the leaders. Even in countries with a strong authoritarian government, those in power must at least consider some aspects of popular opinion. This segment of the population is called the "selective" by political economists and is the only segment that matters to politicians. It could be an economic elite or military forces under a dictatorship, but either fits the bill here. In a representative democracy, there will be voters and other interest groups. No matter who matters, officials need the support of their constituents to stay in office. The diversity of voting systems in democracies affects the way politicians experience the demands of the electorate. The temporal horizons of politicians can be helped along with the existence of organized political parties. While a single

politician may simply be concerned about the next election, a political party should be concerned with its image for a longer period of time. When politicians are elected by the people of the country as a whole, as in countries like Israel and the Netherlands, the main concern is the general policy of the country. The general consensus is that "all politics is local " ; this is a phrase typically attributed to Tip O'Neill , the Democratic Speaker of the House of Representatives who served in the 1970s and 1980s . This is the case in the United States House of Representatives, where politicians represent more restricted geographic areas.

Various electoral systems have the potential to shift political discourse to either more national or more local issues. The type of voters politicians must bring to court to win elections is shaped in part by the electoral institutions present. The Electoral College in the United States gives voters who fall somewhere at the center of the political spectrum in the industrial states of the Midwest a prominent role in presidential elections focused on preserving production. In a multi-party parliamentary system, the voter with the most say may be supporters of a small party capable of oscillating between coalition partners. An example of this is the role played by marginal parties in the formation of governments in Israel. The voting system will have a disproportionate impact on politics and whoever decides to make the most important voters. It is also important to consider the nature of legislative institutions. For example, while a unitary parliamentary system has the potential to bring about significant and rapid change, the existing separation of powers in the United States government results in more gradual and longer-lasting change. In federal systems, such as those seen in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Germany, and the United States, a significant amount of power is given to state or state governments , while in centralized systems the national government is given the ability to rule unrivaled. Central banks and public health agencies are two examples of independent entities to which some governments delegate important policy decisions. These organizations are less sensitive to the daily political pressures faced by governments. These institutions are important because of their influence on the relative weights that politicians ascribe to the various groups that make up society. Some of the country's sociopolitical institutions give labor unions considerable power and influence, others give preferential treatment to farmers, while others are controlled by business groups. Political economists examine the many interests at play

as well as the mechanisms by which community institutions transfer and transform these interests into public policy. Even the worst can be the best. All of this is important to policy makers, people who follow politics, and even people who are simply interested in economics, because it has the potential to radically change the way we think about policy and policy advice.

6. Going Back to Free Trade

There is a possibility that the economic policy that will most benefit the economy may not be politically defensible. To return to free trade, almost all economists would advise that the best hope for a small nation is to unilaterally remove all trade barriers. This is the advice most likely to follow. However, a government attempting to move towards unilateral free trade is almost likely to encounter great resistance from private interests as well as a significant portion of the general population who see such a move as dangerous. This is likely to lead to the government's downfall, followed by a new administration that can be relied upon to maintain or even increase existing trade restrictions. In this case, following the strategy initially thought to be the best option may produce a far less desirable outcome. People interested in economic policy, whether they are politicians, analysts, observers, or just average citizens, must analyze not only the economic consequences of policy efforts, but also the political viability of such proposals. If following the first best policy is doomed to fail and perhaps provokes a backlash, then the treatment may actually be worse than the disease it is intended to cure. It is more rational to take into account the political realities that the administration has to deal with and to formulate a policy considering these realities. It is better to accept the second best than to insist on the first best and get something worse; alternatively, it is preferable not to let the pursuit of excellence stand in the way of achieving great results. In the last few decades, some of the most notable changes that have caused widespread debate among social policy students in European examples include the increasing conditionality and individualization of formerly rights-based benefits, the introduction and implementation of welfare markets, the decentralization of welfare provision. and lowering levels of generosity (for example, Bonoli and Natali , 2012; Hemerijck , 2013; Pierson , 2001, 1994; Palier and Hay, 2017).

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In parallel, the economic and social crises that have recurred in western countries over the past few decades have reshaped debates on the citizen's support for the welfare state, as well as party political divisions over the welfare state and its future. albeit in different lights (Giger & Nelson, 2011; Taylor- Gooby & Leruth , 2018).

7. Conclusion

What effects did these shifts in Europe's welfare states have on the political behavior and views of individual peoples? How can these results be explained by the processes currently in place? And what questions does the study of the latter in European examples raise for future research? In this article, we bring together both strands of research into the policies and policies of the welfare state. We will then turn attention to the political consequences of fundamental policy changes, namely people's political participation and views on politics. This review article draws on the academic literature on policy feedback to the masses, combining a focus on policy change and its effects on the political behavior and attitudes of various citizens . In particular, the article examines the effects of policy change on the attitudes and behaviors of young people (Campbell, 2012; Larsen, 2019; Mettler and Soss , 2004). The idea that institutions and policies are relevant to the study of politics is at the center of what is known as the policy feedback literature . Institutions and policies allocate resources to people, encourage them, convey messages and information, and anchor normative ideas and expectations; All these factors contribute to the formation of individuals' political behaviors and attitudes (Pierson , 1993; Mettler and Welch , 2004; Svallfors , 2006). The impact of welfare policy on party elections and electoral competition has been explored in previous studies (for example, Giger , 2012; Van Kersbergen et al. 2014), as well as support and attitudes towards certain social programs (Busemeyer and Neimanns , 2017). ; Kumlin and Stadelmann-Steffen , 2014; Jordan, 2013; Van Oorschot and Meuleman , 2014; Garritzmann , 2015). More recently, Larsen (2019) examined the magnitude of feedback effects on political participation and attitudes in various social policies, and Busemeyer and colleagues (2021) detailed a typology of policy feedback on policy attitudes. Both of these studies were done more recently. There is a need for more studies on this subject, especially in Turkish.

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